

AIRCRAFT MAINTENANCE ENGINEERING: A TALK WITH AN EXPERT

Vijay Bhat

What is the field of Aircraft Maintenance Engineering?

Aircraft Maintenance Engineer (AME) keeps an airplane airworthy, which means it is fit to fly safely. To do this, they inspect, maintain, and repair the aircraft. Aircraft radio avionics (electronics), navigation, communication, electrical, and mechanical systems. It is a critical aspect of aviation safety, as even a minor malfunction or defect can have serious consequences.

What maintenance is required for an aircraft?

Types of required maintenance vary by class and type of aircraft, generally classified as line maintenance, heavy maintenance, and shop or component maintenance. Line maintenance covers pre-flight checks, daily checks of fluids, scheduled minor repairs, modifications, and troubleshooting.

What are the benefits of being an AME?

Higher earning potential, technological advancements, flight benefits, and the opportunity to work in multiple sectors of aviation.

Which subjects in high school are important to plan a career as an AME?

Mathematics, physics, chemistry, electrical fundamentals, electronics fundamentals, digital techniques, electronic instrument systems, materials and hardware, maintenance practices, and fluency in English.

What is the essential qualification required to become an AME?

A degree or diploma in aeronautical or mechanical or electrical engineering is essential requirement. However, in order to obtain the necessary authorization, one must possess an AME license issued by the Director General of Civil Aviation (DGCA), which is under the jurisdiction of the Government of India.

What knowledge and skills are required for AME?

Understanding of equipment and systems, knowledge of various maintenance techniques, operation analysis, problem solving, critical thinking, computer skills, decision-making, interpersonal skills, and flexibility are some of the essential requirements.

Attention to details, understanding of safety regulations, communication skills (to explain faults to others), time management skills (to work quickly and accurately), analytical thinking, physical fitness, the ability to read and understand technical information, and a strong sense of responsibility are specific job requirements for AME.

What are the job responsibilities of an AME?

AME is responsible for the proper operation of aircraft and their safety.

Summary

Overall, this field is crazy and financially attractive. Hard work is a must; once you get an opportunity to enter the aviation industry, sky is the limit. Keep on learning and updating yourself!

The author has 37 years of experience in the aviation industry, making him a knowledgeable authority on aircraft maintenance engineering. He began his professional life at Air India, where he eventually rose through the ranks to become a senior manager.

email address: vijaybhat33@gmail.com

